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EXPERIMENTAL DIABETIC ANIMAL MODELS FOR STUDYING DIABETES

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ANNOTATION

Diabetes is a metabolic disorder that occurs due to decreased insulin levels and increased blood sugar levels. The disease is chronic and often has a risk of exacerbation. Conditions caused by diabetes can be fatal (hyperglycemic and hypoglycemic coma). According to statistics, diabetes is the second most common metabolic disorder after obesity. Diabetes occurs due to a lack of insulin. This disease is characterized by metabolic disorders of proteins, carbohydrates and fats. Insulin promotes the breakdown, synthesis and use of glycogen in the liver, and prevents the breakdown of carbohydrate compounds. In the process of protein metabolism, insulin initiates the synthesis of proteins and nucleic acids, preventing protein breakdown. The effect of insulin on fat metabolism is that it increases the rate of glucose entry into hepatocytes, activates cellular energy processes, slows down the breakdown of fats and improves the synthesis of fatty acids.

Key words: *diabetes, alloxan, streptozotocin, insulin, beta cells.*

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic condition of hyperglycemia, which occurs as a result of impaired carbohydrate metabolism due to absolute or relative insulin deficiency and is manifested by glucosuria, polyuria, polydipsia, impaired lipid, protein, mineral metabolism, and the development of acute and chronic complications.

Diabetes mellitus is divided into 2 types:

Type I - insulin-dependent (20%);

Type II - non-insulin-dependent (80%).

Insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus is caused by an absolute deficiency of insulin in the body and is also observed in children. In this type of diabetes mellitus, ketoacidosis develops and is treated with insulin.

Type II, which is not insulin-dependent, occurs in adults, is manifested by a relative deficiency of insulin, is not complicated by ketoacidosis, and does not require insulin therapy.

Currently, diabetes mellitus (DM) continues to occupy one of the leading places among the so-called “diseases of civilization” in terms of growth rates of morbidity, disability and mortality. According to the latest data, in 2013 there were 382 million people with diabetes in the world, and according to forecasts, the number of such patients may increase to 592 million by 2035, i.e. by 55% [13]. DM is a chronic disease characterized by a relative or absolute absence of insulin, which leads to hyperglycemia. Chronic hyperglycemia contributes to the development of various complications, such as neuropathy, nephropathy and retinopathy, and the risk of cardiovascular diseases also increases. According to the modern classification, there are two main types of DM, which have numerous clinical, immunological and genetic differences.

Approximately 10% of all cases of diabetes mellitus are type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) [11], which develops as a result of the death of β -cells of the pancreas, leading to the cessation of insulin production, a key regulator of carbohydrate and lipid metabolism in the body. Despite numerous studies aimed at studying this disease, the disease continues to progress, and the insufficient number of means for the prevention and treatment of T1DM suggests the inclusion of these patients in high-risk groups for the development of a huge number of complications, which is confirmed by data on the overall risk of mortality among people with diabetes, which is twice as high as that of peers without diabetes [6]. Among the complications, it is worth noting the negative impact on the female reproductive system, manifested in the form of menstrual irregularities, infertility, pathological course of pregnancy and childbirth [12,16].

Chemical models of diabetes mellitus are the most widely used in modern experimental diabetology. According to literary data, in works published in the field of entopharmacology for the decade from 1996 to 2006, streptozotocin and alloxan were used as chemical agents for studying various aspects of the disease in 69% of cases and in 31% of cases [2].

Alloxan is a breakdown product of uric acid and is a white crystalline substance that turns pink in the air. The agent has a diabetogenic effect only when administered parenterally - intravenously, subcutaneously, intramuscularly and intraperitoneally. It is used to study type 1 diabetes mellitus. The effective dose depends on the type of animal, the method of administration and the nutritional status [3,4].

Mechanism of action of alloxan. Despite a significant number of studies confirming the selective damage of beta cells by alloxan, there is no generally accepted theory that comprehensively explains this phenomenon. There are several hypotheses

of the mechanism of action of alloxan. According to one of them, proposed by A. Lazarow, alloxan causes selective damage to the permeability of the beta cell plasmalemma due to its reaction with dithiol groups necessary to maintain the integrity of the membranes. As a result, the structure of the cell membrane changes. Spaces are formed in it through which the cells lose potassium, coenzymes and enzymes, and extracellular sodium enters. Metabolism in beta cells is disrupted, and they die. The hypothesis was confirmed in experiments conducted in vitro by D. Watkins et al. [1]. However, some of its assumptions were subsequently subjected to critical analysis [9]. It was obvious that the effect of alloxan depends not only on the inhibitory effect on the SH groups of the plasmalemma. According to modern scientific research, in animals with alloxan-induced diabetes, the ratio between essential macro- and microelements (sodium, potassium, calcium, zinc, iron, copper, etc.) is disrupted [19].

There are many models of spontaneous development of type 1 diabetes in rodents (biobreeding, LETL, WBN/Kob rats, NOD mice, etc.) and type 2 diabetes (rats and mice with a defect in leptin or leptin receptor synthesis, etc.), obtained as a result of inherited genetic mutations or selected from outbred animals without diabetes (for example, Goto-Kakizaki rats, Tsumara Suzuki mice, etc.) [15, 18]. Diabetes mellitus can be caused surgically (by means of partial or total pancreatectomy, a classic example of which is the experiment of O. Minkowski and J. Mering on dogs [17], by pharmacological drugs (causing the destruction of insulin-secreting beta cells of the pancreas [5]), by using genetic engineering methods (knockout technology and transgenic hyperexpression of specific genes [15]), by prescribing special dietary rations [8,14], as well as various combinations of these.

Streptozotocin (N-nitroso derivative of glucosamine, gross formula $C_8H_{15}N_3O_7$) is a broad-spectrum antibiotic and, like alloxan, is a structural analogue of glucose. As a result of intraperitoneal or intravenous administration, STC is transferred to the β -cells of the pancreas by the GLUT-2 transporter and causes DNA alkylation. Subsequent activation of poly(ADP-ribose) synthetase leads to depletion of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD^+), a decrease in the cellular level of adenosine triphosphate, cell necrosis and subsequent inhibition of insulin production and the development of insulin resistance [18]. Negative manifestations are accompanied by activation of free radical oxidation due to excessive formation of nitric oxide [10]. Unlike alloxan, when modeling diabetes by administering optimally selected doses of STC to animals, it is possible to achieve significantly less destruction of β -cells compared to that with the introduction of alloxan.

Carbohydrate metabolism disorders in diabetes mellitus are manifested by: damage to hexokinases (hepato-, myo- and adipocytes); increased glycogenolysis; activation of gluconeogenesis; impaired Krebs cycle activity.

Lipid metabolism disorders in diabetes mellitus are manifested by: impaired glucose utilization; impaired lipogenesis; 3) mobilization of fats from depots; lipemia; increased ketogenesis and cholesterologenesi; ketone brain and cholesterolemia; ketonuria.

Protein metabolism disorders in diabetes mellitus are manifested by: impaired glucose utilization; increased protein breakdown; aminoacidemia, high demand for glucogenic amino acids; increased gluconeogenesis.

The following biochemical changes are observed in diabetes mellitus: hyperglycemia; glucosuria; ketonemia, ketonuria, atherosclerosis; ketoacidosis; hyperaminoacidemia and aminoaciduria; polyuria; polydipsia; polyphagia; dehydration. Taking into account the above, it can be said that the use and improvement of experimental animal models of diabetes mellitus is necessary for the development of new approaches to modeling this disease, as well as for studying the effectiveness of various drugs.

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